

Soil Health & Soil Heritage

prioritisation and instrument review

Identifying Priorities

The core project group, representing researchers in environment, archaeology, agriculture, and sensor development worked over three days to identify and rank shared priorities for the collection of remote and near surface sensing data, considering a broad range of mapping and monitoring applications related to the management of agricultural landscapes. For each thematic application area, the ability to assess and monitor specific soil and related environmental properties was considered.

priority	high	requirements per application per parameter				
	medium	soil carbon	agricultural	soil properties (nutrients, compaction, etc)	water	buried archaeology
cross-domain priority	low					
medium - high	soil acidity / pH					
high	soil moisture					
medium	soil temperature					
medium	soil compaction					
low	magnetism					
medium - high	Bulk density					
high	soil chemistry / nutrients					
uncertain	VOC					
medium	water table level					
high	salinity					
medium	soil CO2 and methane (GHG)					
high	topography					
high	organic carbon					
medium	local climate					
medium	micro climate					

cross_domain_priorities_chart < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/cross_domain_priorities_chart.xlsx>

DOWNLOAD < [HTTPS://IPAAST-CZO.GLASGOW.AC.UK/WP-CONTENT/UPLOADS/2022/06/CROSS_DOMAIN_PRIORITIES_CHART.XLSX](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/cross_domain_priorities_chart.xlsx)>

Instrument Review

The group reviewed a range of instruments and assessed their capacity to produce data relevant for mapping and monitoring applications identified as high or medium-high cross-domain priorities. This exercise provided an overview of obstacles to producing useful data and identified high potential instruments.

Some of the most common capability short-comings in soil data sampling tools (sensing/imaging) in being able to provide useful data across different disciplines

cross-domain priority	soil carbon (sequestration in z direction)	soil carbon (environment)	agricultural	water	buried archaeology
high	Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Sensoterra (mn), Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Sensoterra (mn), Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Dualem (mp), Sensoterra (mn), Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Sensoterra (mn), Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Dualem (mp), Sensoterra (mn), Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)
high	soil moisture	BaySpec HS sensor (mp), soiloptix (mp)	BaySpec HS sensor (mp), soiloptix (mp)	BaySpec HS sensor (mp), soiloptix (mp)	BaySpec HS sensor (mp), soiloptix (mp)
high	soil chemistry / nutrients	???	???	???	???
high	salinity	Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Dualem (mp)	Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Dualem (mp)	PMA V3 s. can spectro. lysar (mn), in situ Aqua TROLL 600 Multiparameter Sonda (mn)	Van Walt Pico probe (mn), Dualem (mp)
high	topography	lidar / rtk gps (mp)	lidar / rtk gps (mp)	lidar / rtk gps (mp)	lidar / rtk gps (mp)
high	organic carbon	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), agrocares (mn)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), agrocares (mn)	in-situ Aqua TROLL 600 Multiparameter Sonda (mn), PMA V3 s. can spectro. lysar (mn)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp)
high	local climate	Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)	Decentlab DL-ATM41-001 (mn)
medium - high	soil acidity / pH	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), Agrocares (mn)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), Agrocares (mn)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), agrocares (mn)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), agrocares (mn)
medium - high	soil compaction	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), topsoil mapper (mp), Dualem (mp)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), topsoil mapper (mp), Dualem (mp)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), topsoil mapper (mp), Dualem (mp)	Veris MSP3 (mp), Soiloptix (mp), topsoil mapper (mp), Dualem (mp)
medium - high	Bulk density	soiloptix (mp)	soiloptix (mp)	soiloptix (mp)	soiloptix (mp)
medium	soil temperature	GroPoint Profile probe (mn), Sensoterra (mn), Van Walt Pico probe (mn)	Sensoterra (mn), Van Walt Pico probe (mn)	Sensoterra (mn), Van Walt Pico probe (mn)	Sensoterra (mn), Van Walt Pico probe (mn)
medium	water table level	Rugged Troll (mn), DECENTlab water pressure sensor (mn)	Rugged Troll (mn), DECENTlab water pressure sensor (mn)	Rugged Troll, DECENTlab water pressure sensor	Rugged Troll (mn), DECENTlab water pressure sensor (mn)
medium	soil CO2 and methane (GHG)	Licor LI-7810 CH4/CO2/H2O Trace Gas Analyzer (mn), Licor 850 (mn)	Licor LI-7810 CH4/CO2/H2O Trace Gas Analyzer (mn), Licor 850 (mn)	Licor 850 (mn)	Licor LI-7810 CH4/CO2/H2O Trace Gas Analyzer (mn), Licor 850 (mn)

cross_domain_instruments < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/cross_domain_instruments.xlsx>

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A complete version of the draft instrument review document is provided below. Refinement of this document through further review of publicly available information

on instruments and feedback from colleagues working in land management is ongoing.

[SENSORS-FOR-SOIL-HEALTH-AND-ARCHAEOLOGY-draft < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/SENSORS-FOR-SOIL-HEALTH-AND-ARCHAEOLOGY-draft.xlsx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/SENSORS-FOR-SOIL-HEALTH-AND-ARCHAEOLOGY-draft.xlsx)

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Contributors: Eamonn Baldwin, Ying Zheng, Awais Asiz Shab, Analito Michala, Rachael Wakefield, Rachel Opitz

The instrument review informed follow on workshops in Dalswinton and Glasgow.

University
of Glasgow

This project was supported by funding from NERC (DISCIPLINE HOPPING) – award 317545.

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